

Supplemental File 2: Data items requested from the extract.

Data item	Definition
Demographics and clinical factors	
Year of birth	
Year of diabetes diagnosis	
Date of 1 st day of course	
Gender	Whether the individual identifies themselves as male or female.
Ethnic minority	Whether the patient identifies themselves as belonging to an ethnic minority group
HbA1c*	HbA1c test result as mmol/mol
HbA1c result date*	Date of HbA1c result
Weight*	
Height	
DKA total	Total number of DKA episodes requiring admission experienced by the patient since diagnosis
DKA year*	Number of DKA episodes requiring admission experienced by the patient in the 12 months before the course
Hypo self-treat*	Whether in the last year patient had a hypoglycaemic episode they were unable to treat themselves i.e., had someone to help
Hypo self-treat last year*	Total number of hypoglycaemic episodes in the last year unable to treat themselves
Hypo paramedic*	Total number of hypoglycaemic episodes in the last year requiring paramedic assistance
Hypo A&E*	Total number of hypoglycaemic episodes in the last year requiring hospital admission
Symptoms occurrence*	Blood glucose level when patient usually experiences symptoms of hypoglycaemia
Method of insulin delivery*	
MDI days attended	Number of days of course attended (MDI formats)
Pump days attended	Number of days of course attended (Pump formats)
Course formats	
Standard DAFNE	Delivered as 1 week Mon- Fri
5x1 DAFNE	Delivered 1 day per week over 5 weeks
Pump DAFNE	Delivered as 1 week Mon- Fri
Remote DAFNE (fully remote)	Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered virtually
Remote DAFNE (blended)	Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered either face to face or a blend of face to face and virtual
Remote Pump (fully remote)	Online self-directed learning weeks 1-4. Group sessions weeks 1-5 delivered virtually
Repeater	Delivered as 1 week Mon- Fri
Form of diabetes	Whether the patient is repeating a DAFNE course
	Type of diabetes if not type 1

*Data item available pre and post course